

Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Evaluation of Musculoskeletal TumorsNath A^{1*}, Pegu BJ², Kutum T³¹Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Radiology, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam^{2,3}Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam

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Abstract:

Bone tumors and tumor-like lesions are frequently encountered by radiologists. Although radiographs are the primary screening technique, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can help narrow the differential or make a specific diagnosis when a lesion is indeterminate or shows signs of aggressiveness. MRI can extend the diagnostic evaluation by demonstrating several tissue components. Even when a specific diagnosis cannot be made, the differential diagnosis can be narrowed. MRI is superior to the other imaging modalities in detecting bone marrow lesions and tumoral tissue (faint lytic/sclerotic bone lesions can be difficult to visualize using only radiographs). Contrast-enhanced MRI can reveal the most vascularized parts of the tumor and MRI guidance makes it possible to avoid biopsying necrotic areas. MRI is very helpful in local staging and surgical planning by assessing the degree of intramedullary extension and invasion of the adjacent physal plates, joints, muscle compartments and neurovascular bundles. It can be used in assessing response to neoadjuvant therapy and further restaging. The post-therapeutic follow-up should also be done using MRI. Despite the high quality of MRI, there are a few pitfalls and limitations of which one should be aware. Applications of MRI in bone tumors will probably continue to grow as new sequences are further studied.

Keywords: Magnetic resonance imaging, Bone neoplasms, Diagnosis, Neoplasm staging, Follow-up.

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Introduction

The term bone tumor is a broad category, encompassing benign and malignant neoplasms, reactive focal abnormalities, metabolic abnormalities, and miscellaneous “tumorlike” conditions. The location of the tumor and the patient's age are the two most crucial factors in evaluating a bone tumor. Without even examining any photos, this information alone can be used to restrict the differential diagnosis. The particular radiographic appearance will therefore frequently result in the single accurate diagnosis and aid further reduces the list.

The method for radiographic diagnosis of bone tumors involves systematically examining the lesion and taking note of various distinct radiographic characteristics [1–5]. Although these characteristics were first explained in relation to how the lesion appeared on traditional radiographs, computed tomographic (CT) scans can also be used to apply them [6].

Nevertheless, they are inapplicable to magnetic resonance (MR) images, since marrow and soft-tissue edema can overstate the severity of certain benign lesions on MR images [7–9]. Tumor location, borders and zone of transition, periosteal reaction, mineralization, size and number of

lesions, and presence of a soft-tissue component are the specific radiographic findings that need to be assessed.

Case Series

Case 1- Unicameral bone cyst/ Simple bone cyst (SBC): Unicameral bone cysts account for 3% of benign bone tumors [10]. The most frequent consequences are recurrent pathologic fractures and bone growth abnormalities because the site is frequently metaphyseal and adjacent to the physis; spontaneous healing happens in 5%–10% of instances [11–13]. Reducing the chance of a pathologic fracture and accelerating osseous healing are the main objectives of percutaneous treatment for unicameral bone cysts. Unicameral bone cysts have been managed by a number of percutaneous procedures, such as intralesional steroid injection, autologous bone marrow concentrate, bone allograft, and demineralized bone matrix [14–16].

The most helpful modality for examining the internal structure of the lesions is magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), thanks to its excellent soft tissue contrast and multiplanar views. When a cyst is real, only its epithelial covering shows up

well on MRI; contrast-enhanced MRI shows no enhancement at all in the interior of the cyst [17]. Due to its non-epithelial lining, SBC may be distinguished from actual cysts with epithelial linings using contrast-enhanced MRI. Generally speaking, benign tumors—which need to be

differentiated from SBCs—have solid contents, whereas SBCs are typically filled with fluid. Therefore, by examining the signal intensity (SI) on MRI, SBCs can be identified apart from benign tumors.

Figure 1: This humeral lesion in a 17 yr boy is showing a) low signal intensity in T1WI b) high signal in T2FS WI. c) T1FS gadolinium-based contrast medium-enhanced sequence showed peripheral enhancement, typical of liquid content, favouring the diagnosis of a solitary bone cyst.

Case 2- Aneurysmal bone cyst (ABC): Primary aneurysmal bone cysts are benign neoplasms that in 75% of cases affect patients younger than 20 years of age [10]. The metaphysis of the long bone, the spine (usually the posterior components), and the pelvis are the common sites of primary aneurysmal bone cysts [10].

Due to the highly vascular nature of the tissue and sometimes difficult anatomic locations, surgical resection can be difficult to accomplish total excision, control of bleeding, weakening and instability of the bone, and damage to surrounding

structures. There is also a significant risk of recurrence [12]. Magnetic resonance imaging demonstrates fluid-fluid levels. Low T1 and T2 signal rims can be seen on T1contrast-enhanced and T2 weighted images, which highlight the septa within the lesion [18]. Multiple focal areas of hyperintense signal on T1 and T2 weighted sequences indicate the presence of variable age blood within the cystic cavities; double density fluid levels may also be observed. Osseous and soft tissue edema may indicate the presence of a pathologic fracture.

Figure 2: Expansile multiloculated cystic lytic lesion is seen involving C4 vertebra which is replacing whole of the body, lamina, pedicle, transverse process and spinal process causing moderate spinal canal stenosis and spinal cord indentation posteriorly. The lesion shows multiple internal fluid- fluid levels on c)

axial STIR, d) sagittal T2WI and e) STIR sequences, with no intervening soft tissue or thick septations, suggesting aneurysmal bone cyst.

Case 3- Fibrous dysplasia (FD): The distribution of FD lesions depends on the form of the disease. Monostotic FD accounts for about 80% of patients with FD. The most common location of monostotic FD is the rib, skull and femur. In the polyostotic form, the skull, mandible, pelvic bones and femur are the most frequently affected sites. While the majority of bony lesions in polyostotic FD become non-silent and clinically significant by the age of 10, virtually no new lesions appear after the age of 15. Many cases of monostotic FD are discovered incidentally, whereas the polyostotic form is typically diagnosed during the first few years of life. FD does not consistently show hypointense signal intensities on T1- and T2-weighted images (WI) as might be expected (19). Signal intensity on T1- and T2-WI and the degree of contrast

enhancement depend on the amount and degree of bony trabeculae, cellularity, collagen, and cystic and hemorrhagic changes. Sharply defined borders and intermediate to low signal intensity on T1-WI and intermediate to high intensity on T2-WI are typical features of FD lesions. The T2 signal decreases with increasing bony trabeculae count and increases with decreasing bony trabeculae count.

Additionally, tiny cystic regions that brighten the T2 signal can be found in FD lesions. On postcontrast T1-WI, all lesions exhibited some degree of enhancement. Whereas inactive lesions exhibit a milder enhancement, active lesions exhibit an avid enhancement (20). The enhancement pattern could be homogeneous, rim, patchy in the center, or a combination of these.

Figure 3- A multiloculated intramedullary g) T1 hypointense and h) STIR hyperintense lesion is noted in the proximal metaphysis and upper 1/3rd of diaphysis of left humerus showing i) peripheral enhancement on post contrast study. STIR hyperintensity is noted in the proximal epiphysis of the left humerus, suggesting edema.

Case 4- Ewing's sarcoma: Ewing's sarcomas are common bone tumors in children [21]. EES is less common, more frequently observed in older adults and children, and frequently has a worse prognosis [22,23]. Similar to its intraosseous counterpart, extraosseous Ewing's sarcoma (EES), which was initially reported in 1969, is a malignant mesenchymal tumor. These tumors are typically found in the deep soft tissues of the extremities or in the paravertebral regions; the lower extremities are more likely than the upper extremities to develop these tumors [21]. Individuals diagnosed with EES frequently report a rapidly expanding soft-tissue mass, of which approximately one-third is painful due to nearby structures being compressed. In the second decade of life, they

frequently manifest. There is a slight preference for Caucasians and a male predominance.

No evidence of environmental or familial influence has been found [24–27]. A mass with signal intensity comparable to skeletal muscle on T1-weighted imaging has been observed on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (21, 28); internal hemorrhage areas may be observed as high T1 signal [21,28]. The mass frequently shows a heterogeneous intermediate to hyperintense signal on T2-weighted images. High T2 signal regions are frequently found at the sites of cystic or necrotic alterations. In postcontrast images, heterogeneous enhancement is frequently seen. It is also possible to observe high-flow vascular channels or flow

voids, which are very typical but not specific to EES.

Figure 4: An expansile bone lesion centered in the upper half of left fibula with a soft tissue component, showing j) heterogeneous signal intensity on T1WI, k) isointense on T2WI and l) heterogeneous enhancement on post contrast study. Surrounding muscles appears edematous. Tumor shows extension into the posterolateral epiphysis of ipsilateral tibia. T1WI also shows lamellated periosteal reaction, suggesting it to be Ewing's sarcoma.

Case 5- Osteosarcoma: Osteosarcoma (OS) is a malignant tumor of connective tissue that produces osteoid matrix and variable amounts of cartilage matrix and fibrous tissue [29]. OS is the most common primary bone tumor in children and adolescents (4.4 cases per million persons per year), although it makes up less than 1% of all cancers diagnosed in the United States (30-32). Seven unique primary subtypes of osteosarcoma are recognized in the World Health Organization classification system: high-grade surface osteosarcomas, parosteal, periosteal, small cell, conventional, and telangiectatic osteosarcomas [33]. The most prevalent subtype of osteosarcoma, known as conventional or classic osteosarcoma, accounts for 75–80% of all cases [34,35]. Elevated surface subtypes, uncommon in kids [33,34]. A less common intramedullary subtype, telangiectatic osteosarcoma accounts for 2%–12% of cases [36-38] and can occasionally be misdiagnosed as an

aneurysmal bone cyst [38]. In contrast to intramedullary osteosarcomas, which are confined within the medullary cavity, surface osteosarcomas "sit" on the surface of the bone. The rare childhood forms of surface osteosarcomas include parosteal, periosteal, and high-grade surface subtypes [33,34].

MRI is the preferred imaging modality for characterizing tumor bulk and extent of local invasion. Due to the intrinsic fatty elements of bone marrow, intramedullary tumors are best visualized on T1-weighted MR images where they appear as a low signal intensity area against a background of otherwise higher signal intensity [38–41]. On fluid-sensitive (T2-weighted fat-suppressed or short-tau inversion-recovery) MR images, the extent of the intramedullary tumor is overestimated in as many as 73% of cases [41, 42]. To describe tumor heterogeneity and show regions of cystic degeneration and necrosis, postcontrast T1-weighted MR images can be utilized.

Figure 5: A large ill-defined lesion is noted involving the right femoral diaphysis with extension into the medullary cavity and epi-metaphyseal region limited by the physal plate, with large soft tissue component which appears m) T1 isointense with areas of hyperintensity (suggesting Haemorrhagic foci) and n) T2 heterogeneously hyperintense intermixed with intermixed areas of hypointensity (suggesting osteoid matrix). o) T1FS gadolinium-based contrast medium-enhanced sequence showed heterogeneously enhancement. Soft tissue component invasion is noted into the muscles of anterior, middle and posterior component of upper and mid-thigh which is extending caudally till midshaft of femur and extending cranially till the ischiopubic rami. Features suggesting Osteosarcoma.

Case 6- Metastasis: Bone metastasis is frequently observed in the most relevant types of solid tumors representing an important imaging target for detection and follow-up. For this purpose, morphologic aspects of skeletal lesions are assessed by conventional X-rays, CT, and MRI, whereas bone scintigraphy and SPECT reveal changes of bone remodeling.

Most relevant types of solid tumors frequently show evidence of bone metastasis. Of these, skeletal metastatic lesions are present in about 70% of breast and prostate cancer patients who pass away from their illness. As a result, one of the most frequent locations for cancer to spread is to the skeleton. As a result, patients with skeletal complications like pathologic fractures, spinal cord

compression, and hypercalcemia have much lower quality of life. Compared to other imaging modalities, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is particularly sensitive and specific in detecting bone metastases because of its superior soft-tissue contrast. Since tumor growth frequently happens before bone deterioration, malignant bone marrow infiltration can be detected by MRI even before morphologic bone changes are noticeable. Osteolytic disease is frequently associated with hypo- or isointense T1 and hyperintense T2 signals, as well as relatively strong contrast media uptake, which is indicative of the extent of tumor infiltration of the bone marrow. These findings are frequently the result of tumor proliferation in the bone marrow.

Figure 6: Patient is a 57 yr old male with lung cancer, presented with low backache and hip pain. On MRI of pelvis, a large lobulated expansile p) T1-isointense and T2-hyperintense lesion is noted involving

the right iliac wing, extending to involve the ischium and the right ala of sacrum showing q, r) heterogenous enhancement on post-contrast study. The lesion is also noted to infiltrate the surrounding gluteal muscles. Few similar signal intensity lesions also noted involving head, neck and proximal shaft of bilateral femur, showing enhancement on post-contrast study. Few rim-enhancing collections also noted involving the gluteal muscles. Features favouring the diagnosis of a bone metastasis.

Case 7- Tenosynovial Giant-cell tumor:

Tenosynovial giant cell tumor (TGCT) is a fibrohistiocytic soft-tissue tumor that affects anatomical structures such as bursae, tendon sheaths, and joints that are covered in a synovial membrane. Additionally, extra-synovial sites like subcutaneous and intramuscular lesions may be impacted [43]. Pain, edema, stiffness, and restricted function are typical symptoms that lower one's quality of life [44].

TGCT can be categorized based on its growth pattern and site (intra- and extra-articular) [45]. The terms "giant cell tumor of the tendon sheath" and "pigmented villonodular synovitis" were replaced with "localized-type" (L-TGCT) and "diffuse-type" (D-TGCT) in the 2013 World Health Organization classification of soft tissue and bone tumors [43].

MRI is the modality of choice to diagnose D-TGCT. For the purpose of identifying hemosiderin linked to tumor bleeding, a gradient-echo sequence might be useful. Intravenous gadolinium contrast is useful for post-synovectomy follow-up and tumor detection. Because of its heterogeneous histological composition and the range of growth patterns (intra-and/or extra-articular), TGCT can present with variable MRI appearances [45]. Unusual synovial thickening (> 5 mm), usually characterized as "frond-like" with villous or nodular morphology, is one of the findings of D-TGCT [45]. The associated reactive joint effusion is often engulfed by this synovial proliferation, leading to multiloculated thick-walled trapped cystic masses. This is particularly evident in Baker's cysts and the subgastrocnemius synovial recesses, respectively [43].

Figure 7: A s) T1-isointense and t) T2FS- hyperintense lesion is noted on the volar aspect of 3rd digit, adjacent to the middle phalanx, closely abutting the flexor tendon. The lesion shows blooming foci on u) SWI/GRE sequence and shows v) heterogenous enhancement on post-contrast study. However, no hyperintensity is noted involving the substance of the flexor tendon and no underlying bone erosion also seen. Features are consistent with tenosynovial giant cell tumor.

Case 8- Schwannoma: Schwannomas are benign neurogenic tumors that arise from nerve sheath cells. Of all benign soft tissue neoplasms, they are 5% more common in the second to fifth decade of life [46-49]. Intramuscular schwannomas are rare tumors. Intramural schwannomas manifest as a slow-growing soft tissue mass in patients, who may or may not experience accompanying neurological symptoms.

The preoperative diagnosis of intramuscular schwannoma has been found to benefit from MR imaging [47-50]. The split-fat sign, a low signal margin, the fascicular sign, and a hyperintense rim

are MR imaging findings that corroborate the diagnosis of intramuscular schwannoma. The nerve's entry and exit signs are a reliable and frequently observed MR imaging characteristic of schwannomas.

The entry and exit sign forms on T2-weighted MR images due to a hyperintense signal located longitudinally to a fusiform mass.

The distinction between neurofibromas and schwannomas can be made with the aid of MR imaging. Whereas neurofibromas are not encapsulated, Schwannomas are typically located

in an eccentric position within the nerve. When separating benign nerve tumors from malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumors (MPNSTs),

magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the preferred imaging technique.

Figure 8: Fusiform shaped w) T1/T2 isointense mass lesion with few internal cystic changes is noted in the radial side of the wrist, located in the subcutaneous plane, showing y) mild contrast enhancement on post contrast study. The mass lesion has tapered ends with nerves seen leading into and out of the mass possibly cutaneous branch of radial nerve. Possibly schwannoma.

Conclusion

A good knowledge of the characteristic MRI findings of benign and malignant osseous conditions and their role in staging, therapeutic planning and follow-up in the setting of malignancy is essential for optimal patient care.

Bone tumors and tumor-like lesions are frequently encountered by radiologists. Although radiographs are the primary screening technique, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can help narrow the differential or make a specific diagnosis when a lesion is indeterminate or shows signs of aggressiveness.

MRI can extend the diagnostic evaluation by demonstrating several tissue components. Even when a specific diagnosis cannot be made, the differential diagnosis can be narrowed. MRI is superior to the other imaging modalities in detecting bone marrow lesions and tumoral tissue (faint lytic/sclerotic bone lesions can be difficult to visualize using only radiographs). Contrast-enhanced MRI can reveal the most vascularized parts of the tumor and MRI guidance makes it possible to avoid biopsing necrotic areas. MRI is very helpful in local staging and surgical planning by assessing the degree of intramedullary extension and invasion of the adjacent physal plates, joints, muscle compartments and neurovascular bundles.

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